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A BRIF REVIEW ON RAJAVALLABHA NIGHANTU – SCIENTIFIC APPROACH IN DRAVYAGUNA

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Abstract

Nighantu text is one of the important classical textual in the study of *Ayurveda* and especially in the field of *Dravyaguna*. In ancient period of *Samhita* there was less morphological description of plants but after introduction of *Nighantu* it was like a big change in the field of *Dravyaguna Vigyana*. *Ayurveda Nighantu* are compiled to furnish some more information about the terms used in Ayurvedic texts or even their definition. *Rajavallabha Nighantu* is one of them and it is an 18th-century lexicon in *Ayurvedic* Materia medica. It is composed by *Vaidysiromani Shri Rajavallabha* and this work was redacted by *Narayana Das*. This text is classified into six chapter (6 *Pariccheda*) on the basis of division of time of day and night. In comparison to other *Nighantu* this *Nighantu* mainly describes *Dinacharya* (Daily diet regimens) along with that, the concerned drugs and diet. This article is going to explain specificity of *Rajavallabha Nighantu* with its introductory part.

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INTRODUCTION:

Rajavallabha Nighantu is composed by *Vaidysiromani Shri Rajavallabha*. This work was redacted by *Narayana Das*. The redactor *Narayana Das* Period was said to be in 1760 A.D. This text is followed and exemplified the *Shlokas* of *Madanapala Nighantu* and *Bhavprakasha Nighantu*. This work was published by *Shri Khemaraja Shirkrishna Das, Shri Venkateshwara* Steam press, Bombay in *Chaitra Samvat* 1968 Corresponding to 1833 A.D. On the Basis of this, it is placed in 18th century A.D.¹

ABOUT TEXT:

No one in this world knows *Dosha* and *Guna* of each and every substance (*Padartha*), therefore, *Vaidya Shri Rajavallabha* who had knowledge of *Padartha*, wrote this book *Rajavallabha Nighantu*. In the beginning of this *Nighantu*, for the proper completion of *Nighantu* without any obstacles, *Vaidya Shri Rajavallabha* has worshipped the *Nandanandana, Shrigovinda*, the husband of *Lakshmi* in the *Mangalacharana*.

This book is divided in six *Varga* which are named as a *Pariccheda*. Here *Acharya* named *Pariccheda* on the basis of division of time of day and night, i.e. *Prabhatika, Paurvahna, Madhyahna, Aparahna, Nishabhava* and *Aushadha*. Each *Pariccheda* contains different day activity as mentioned in Table No. 1.

Table No. 1: Name and Content of *Pariccheda* from *Rajavallabha Nighantu*²

<i>Pariccheda</i>	Name of <i>Pariccheda</i>	Content
<i>Pratham</i>	<i>Prabhatika</i>	In this <i>Pariccheda Prabhatika Kriya</i> like <i>Saucha, Dantadhayan, Ushna Jala pana</i> etc with <i>Kankati Guna</i> Has been mentioned.
<i>Dvitiya</i>	<i>Paurvahna</i>	In this <i>Pariccheda Purvahaniya Kirya</i> Like, <i>Vyayama, Udagharshana, Danda Dharana</i> etc described in detail with Different <i>Anulepana Dravya</i> .
<i>Tritiya</i>	<i>Madhyahna</i>	In this group he has given detail description about different <i>varga</i> like, <i>Dhanyavarga, Shakavarga, Phalavarga, Matsyavarga, Mamsavarga</i> etc. After <i>Ikshu Varga</i> , he has mentioned <i>Hinguvadi Gana</i> .
<i>Chaturtha</i>	<i>Aparahna</i>	In this chapter the author has described <i>Buddhiguna, Deshaguna, Shadarasaguna</i> , and their basic concept.
<i>Panchama</i>	<i>Nishabhava</i>	Here he explains about <i>Maithuna</i> in details and also given description about <i>Pushpa Guna</i> along with their properties.
<i>Shasti</i>	<i>Aushadha</i>	He has named it as <i>Nanaushadhi Varga</i> wherein he has included all other drugs which are not mentioned in the above division.

Table No. 2: Content and Specialty of *Pariccheda* from *Rajavallabha Nighantu*³

No.	<i>Pariccheda</i> Name	Content	Speciality
1.	<i>Prabhatika</i>	This <i>Pariccheda</i> contains: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Saucha Guna</i> • <i>Ushana jala Pana Guna</i> • <i>Dantadhavan Vidhi</i> • <i>Jihvalekhana Guna</i> • <i>Dantadhavana Nishedha</i> • <i>Chakshudhavana Vidhi</i> • <i>Anjana Guna</i> • <i>Ushniya Dharana Guna</i> • <i>Smanshrunakhadi Chedana Guna</i> • <i>Agni Sevana Guna</i> • <i>Dhuma Hima Guna</i> • <i>Shishir Guna</i> • <i>Avasthana Guna</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dantadhavana Nishedha Dravya:</i> <i>Guvaka, Tala, Hintala, Kharjura, Ketaki, Narikela, Tada.</i> • <i>Danta Dhavane Disha Nirnaya:</i> <i>Dakshina- Mrutyu Paschima- Amaya Purva- Sampada</i> • <i>Kankati</i> (कंकती) : <i>Krantijanani, Kandughni, Murdharogajita, Keshaprasadani, Keshya, Rajo-Jantu-Malapaha</i> • <i>Prabhata Kale Drashtavya:</i> <i>Vaidhya, Purohita, Mantri, Daiva</i> • <i>Kunjati</i> (कुञ्जटि) : <i>Ruksha, Tamoguna pradhana, Kaphapittala</i>
2.	<i>Paurvahna</i>	This <i>Pariccheda</i> contains: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Chatradi Panchakam</i> • <i>Vrushti Guna</i> • <i>Atapa Guna</i> • <i>Chaya Guna</i> • <i>Danda Dharana</i> • <i>Vyayama</i> • <i>Vyayama Nishedha</i> • <i>Ati-vyayama Dosha</i> • <i>Angamardana</i> • <i>Udagharshana</i> • <i>Patha Bhramana</i> • <i>Bhramana</i> • <i>Padatrana Dharana</i> • <i>Hastyadi Gamana Guna</i> • <i>Pada Prakshalana Guna</i> • <i>Pragavata Guna</i> • <i>Dakshina Maruta Guna</i> • <i>Pacchim Pavana Guna</i> • <i>Uttara Vayu Guna</i> • <i>Abhyanga Guna</i> • <i>Padabhyanga Guna</i> • <i>Shiro Mardana Guna</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Paduka Adharana Dosha:</i> <i>Anarogyama, Anayushyama, Indriyaghnama, Adrasthtikruta</i> • <i>Vishrama Guna:</i> <i>Balakruta, Shramanuta, Swasthyada, Shubha</i> • <i>Viswa Vayu Guna:</i> <i>Anayushya, Anaikadoshkruta, Hradya Utpatakara</i> • <i>Tala Phalodbhava Jala:</i> <i>Pittajita, Shukrastanya Vridhdhikara, Guru</i> • <i>Ushna Jala Vishesa Guna:</i> <i>Padahina- Vataghna Ardhahina-Pittaghna Padashesha-Kaphaghna</i> • <i>Rutu Bheda Ushna jala:</i> <i>Hemanta – Padahina Shishira- Padahina Vasanta- Padasthita Sharada-Ardhavshesha Grishma- Ardhavshesha</i> • <i>Dravya Vishesa Snana Guna:</i> <i>Madhuka, Amalaka- Pittaghna, Timirahara Vacha, Musta-kaphaghna, Timirahara Krushna Tila- Chakshushya,</i>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Karna Tail Purana</i> • <i>Udavartana</i> • <i>Vyanjana Anila Guna: Talavrunta, Vansha, Vala, Mayura Pankha</i> • <i>Tail Guna: Tila, Sarshapa, Eranda, Atsi, Kusumbha, Karanja, Nimba</i> • <i>Jala Guna: Surya-chandra Kirana Samyukta Jala, Anavarta Megha Jala, Anupa-Jangala-Sadharana Desha Jala, Nadi, Vapi, Sarovara, Tadagaja ect.</i> • <i>Shada Ritu Jala</i> • <i>Paryushita Jala</i> • <i>Suvasita Jala</i> • <i>Snana Guna</i> • <i>Vastradi Dharana Guna</i> • <i>Anulepana: Chandana, Agaru, Kumkum, Kasturi, Tejapatra, Shati, Kankola etc.</i> 	<p><i>Anilapaha</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Darpana Guna: Shrimada, Ayushya, Papo Upashamanam Param</i>
3.	<i>Madhyahna</i>	<p>This <i>Pariccheda</i> contains:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dhanya Varga</i> • <i>Shaka Varga</i> • <i>Pushpa Shaka</i> • <i>Phala Shaka</i> • <i>Nadi Shaka</i> • <i>Mula Shaka</i> • <i>Phala Varga</i> • <i>Matsya Varga</i> • <i>Mamsa Varga</i> • <i>Madhya Varga</i> • <i>Mutra Varga</i> • <i>Madhu Varga</i> • <i>Kshira Varga</i> • <i>Dadhi Varga</i> • <i>Takra Varga</i> • <i>Navanita Varga</i> • <i>Ghruta Varga</i> • <i>Ekshu Varga</i> • <i>Hingvadi Guna: Hingu, Jiraka, Dhanayaka,</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Dhanya Paka:</i> <i>Hemanta- Shali</i> <i>Grishma- Shasthika</i> <i>Varsha- Vrihi</i> • <i>Kalama Dhanya:</i> <i>Rakta Vikara, Tridoshghna, Chakshushya, Kashya</i> • <i>Rutu Sandhidbhava Dhanya:</i> <i>Ushna, Pittala, Kaphanashana</i> • <i>Grishma Sundara Shaka:</i> <i>Tikta, Rochana, Kaphajita</i> • <i>Limpaka</i> (लिम्पाक-नींबू): <i>Sugandhita, Swadu, Natyamla, Bhakta Rochakama, Vatashleshmahara, Hadya, Chardighna, Nati-pittakruta.</i> • <i>Bahuvara Phala:</i> <i>Hima, Vrushya, Shleshmala, Madhura, Guru</i> • <i>Chiruphala</i> (चीरुफल): <i>Rochana, Amla, Vidahi, Kaphapittakruta.</i> • <i>Madhujata Sharkara</i> (मधुजातशर्करा): <i>Ruksha, Trushna, Chrdi, Atisarajita</i> • <i>Manushya Dadhi:</i> <i>Madhura, Balya,</i>

		<i>Haridra, Shatapushpa, Yavani, Pippali etc.</i>	<i>Snigdha, Santarpanakruta</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manushya Ghruta: <i>Chakshushya, Laghu, Pramehajita, Murcha-Kustha-Visha-Unmada-Graha-Apasmara Nashanam</i>
4.	<i>Aparahna</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This <i>Pariccheda</i> contains: • <i>Sadhyo Mamsadi Guna</i> • <i>Puti Mamsadi Guna</i> • <i>Jangala, Anupa, Sadharana Desha Guna</i> • <i>Shada Rasa</i> • <i>Vipaka</i> • <i>Viryam</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adhayayanadi Guna (अध्ययनादि गुण): <i>Satata Adhyayanam, Vada, Paratantravlokana, Sadvidhya Grahana, Acharya Seva</i> • Buddhi Guna (बुद्धि गुण): <i>Guru Shushruta, Shrivana, Grahana, Dharana, Uhya Upahartha Vignana.</i>
5.	<i>Nishabhava</i>	<p>This <i>Pariccheda</i> contains:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Vaya Bheda Nari Kathana</i> • <i>Maithuna Nishedha</i> • <i>Maithuna Kala Nirnaya</i> • <i>Ati Maithuna Dosha</i> • <i>Shukha Shaya Guna</i> • <i>Pushpa Guna: Malati, Mallika, Dhataki, Ketaki, Shirisha, Padma, Champaka.</i> • <i>Jyotsana – Tamo Guna</i> • <i>Ati Maithuna Guna</i> • <i>Parimita Maithuna Guna</i> • <i>Nindra Guna</i> • <i>Ratri Jagarana Guna</i> • <i>Divaswapna Guna</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Baladi Sansarga Guna: <i>Bala-Pranada Taruni-Pranadharini Prodha- Vruddhatvama Vrudha- Marana</i> • Baladi Maithuna Kala Nirnaya: <i>Grishma, Sharada- Bala Varsha, Vasanta- Prodha Hemanta, Shishira- Na-vruddha</i> • Bhumi Shayya Guna: <i>Vatapittaghni, Bruhani, Shukra Vardhini</i> • Khatava Shayya Guna: <i>Vatala</i> • Pata Shayya Guna: <i>Rukshata, Ativatata</i> • Rangana Pushpa (रंगनपुष्प): <i>Rakta Pittaghni</i> • Maithuna Akarana: <i>Prameha, Meda Granthi, Agnimandhya</i>
6.	<i>Aushadha</i>	<p>This <i>Pariccheda</i> contains:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Bilva</i> • <i>Patala-Shyonaka</i> • <i>Gambhari</i> • <i>Ganikari</i> • <i>Eranda</i> • <i>Gokshura</i> • <i>Kantakari</i> • <i>Bruhati</i> • <i>Shalaparni-Prushnaparni</i> • <i>Bala- Nagabala</i> • <i>Ashwagnadha</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hastikarna: <i>Vrushya, Medha-Ayu-Bala Vardhana</i> • Laksha: <i>Bhagna Sandhanakara, Visarpaghni, Balya, Twakadoshanashini</i> • Prapaundrika: <i>Chakshushya, Shishira, Vranaropaka</i> • Astavarga: <i>Raktapittaghna, Vranaha, Vataoittanuta</i> • Kesharaja: Properties of <i>Kesharaja</i> are similar to <i>Bhringaraja, Vahni Kruccha</i> and <i>Rasayana</i> are two extra properties of <i>Kesharaja</i> • Dandotpala: <i>Swasa-Kasa Jita, Vahni</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Shatavari</i>• <i>Mashaparni- Mudgaparni</i>• <i>Vishala</i>• <i>Sariva</i>• <i>Annanta</i>• <i>Lodhra-Shabara Lodhra</i>• <i>Manjistha</i>• <i>Jivanti</i>• <i>Madhuka</i>• <i>Prasarini</i>• <i>Arjuna</i>• <i>Asthishrunkhala</i>• <i>Bhringaraja</i>• <i>Rudanti</i>• <i>Garikarnika</i>• <i>Bharngi</i>• <i>Kokilaksha</i>• <i>Koshataki</i>• <i>Jyotishmati</i>• <i>Brahmi</i>• <i>Vijaya</i>• <i>Vacha</i>• <i>Shankhapushapi</i>• <i>Shirisha</i>• <i>Durva</i>• <i>Haridra</i>• <i>Daruharidra</i>• <i>Avalgunaja</i>• <i>Edagaja</i>• <i>Karanja</i>• <i>Nimba</i>• <i>Vidanga</i>• <i>Bhurjapatra</i>• <i>Shinshapa</i>• <i>Dhataki</i>• <i>Asana</i>• <i>Mahanimba- Bhunimba</i>• <i>Parpata</i>• <i>Patha</i>• <i>Kutaja - Indrayava</i>• <i>Hibera</i>• <i>Musta</i>• <i>Ativisha</i>• <i>Adraka</i>• <i>Kataphala</i>	<p><i>Dipana</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Talamuli: <i>Vata Vikara Hitakara, Grahani, Rasayana</i>• Dronapushpi: <i>Kapha-Arshoghni, Kamala-Krumi-Sothajita</i>• Vruschikali (वृश्चिकाली): <i>Vishaghni, Kasa- Maruta Nashini</i>• Suryavarta: <i>Vibandhaghna</i>• Renuka: <i>Kaphavataghni, Dipani, Pittakruta, Laghu</i>• Asphota: <i>Vishakusthaghni</i>• Trayamana: <i>Kaphavatanuta</i>• Arkakshira: <i>Krumidoshaghna, Kustha-Udara-Arshajita</i>
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Kustha</i>• <i>Shobhanjana</i>• <i>Katuki</i>• <i>Rasna</i>• <i>Varuna</i>• <i>Paribhadra</i>• <i>Vasa</i>• <i>Guduchi</i>• <i>Pippali- Gajapippali</i>• <i>Chitraka</i>• <i>Danti</i>• <i>Snuhi</i>• <i>Arka</i>• <i>Jayapala</i>• <i>Dhatura</i>• <i>Bhallataka</i>• <i>Guggulu</i>• <i>Sweta & Rakta Trivruta</i>• <i>Rajavruksha</i>• <i>Rohita</i>• <i>Vruddha Daru</i>• <i>Apamarga</i>• <i>Nirgundi</i>• <i>Tulsi</i>• <i>Murva</i>• <i>Vanshalochana</i>• <i>Swarnakshiri</i>• <i>Rutucharya</i>	
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CONCLUSION:

Rajavallabha Nighantu was written by *Vaidya Rajavallabha*, which is famous for describing *Guna* of *Dravya*. This *Nighantu* is Classified in 6 *Pariccheda* that are *Prabhatika*, *Paurvahna*, *Madhyahna*, *Aparahna*, *Nishabhava* and *Aushadha*, based on time division of day and night. Along with this author also mentioned *Dincharya Aushadhi Dravya* concerned with this. *Dantadhavan Disha*, *Kankati Guna*, *Kunjati Guna*, *Dravyavishesh Snana Guna*, *Darpan Guna*, *Madhujata Sharkara Guna*, *Manushya Dadhi & Ghruta Guna*, *Buddhi Guna*, *Baladibhede Maithuna Kala Nirnaya*, *Rangana Pushpa Guna* etc are special contribution of *Rajavallabha Nighantu*. In *Tritiya Paricheda Matsya Varga* and *Mamsa Varga* are described separately which is unique Classification while comparing with other *Samakalina Nighantu*. He has also included some newer drugs like *Hastikarna*, *Kesharaja*, *Dandotpala*, *Vrushikali*, and *Suryavarta* in *Aushadha Pariccheda*.

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REFERENCES

1. Dr. D. Shranthkumar Lucas, An introduction to Nighantu of Ayurveda, Chakhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varansi, Edition-2016, page no-189.
2. Vaidysiromani Shri Rajavallabha, Rajavallabha Nighantu, Kemraja Shrikrushnadas, published by Shri Khemaraja Shirkrishna Das, Shri Venkateshwara Steam press, Bombay.
3. Vaidysiromani Shri Rajavallabha, Rajavallabha Nighantu, Kemraja Shrikrushnadas, published by Shri Khemaraja Shirkrishna Das, Shri Venkateshwara Steam press, Bombay.

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